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Ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) of the Agrafa mountain region in Greece, with additional data on ants from western Thessaly

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Abstract: A list of 99 species and morphospecies of ants collected in 2023 in the Agrafa mountain region, and three sites of western Thessaly is presented. Twenty-seven ant species are new to the investigated region. An updated list of ant species and morphospecies known from Thessaly increased to 134.

Key words: ants, Greece, Thessaly, faunistics.

INTRODUCTION

This paper is a continuation of a series of papers focused on the faunistic investigation of Greek regions. So far, the project has covered Greek islands: Cephalonia (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2014), Corfu (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2021a), Crete (SALATA *et al.* 2020), Dodecanese (BOROWIEC *et al.* 2021), Euboea (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018d), Lemnos (BOROWIEC *et al.* 2022), Lesvos (BOROWIEC *et al.* 2024), Samos (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018b), Samothraki (BOROWIEC *et al.* 2022), Thasos (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2022a, b, BOROWIEC *et al.* 2022), Zakynthos (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018c), and mainland provinces: Epirus (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018a), Peloponnese (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2017a, 2021b, 2024), Thessaly (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018e), and Thrace (BRAČKO *et al.* 2016). Numerous new faunistic data were also given in several faunistic and taxonomic papers (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2012, 2013, CSÖSZ *et al.* 2018, SALATA & BOROWIEC 2017, 2018, 2019a, 2019b, 2019c, 2022, BOROWIEC *et al.* 2023a, b, SALATA *et al.* 2018a, b, 2019, 2021, 2023, 2024, SCUPOŁA & BOROWIEC 2023, DEMETRIOU *et al.* 2023, ZIĘCINA *et al.* 2024).

Agrafa is a mountainous region mainly located in Karditsa regional unit (Thessaly province) and with some parts placed in Evrytania (Sterea Ellas province). It is the southernmost part of the Pindus (or Pindos) mountain range. The range has seven peaks with an altitude reaching over 2,000 meters and several more with an altitude around 1,900 m. Karava is the highest one, with an altitude of 2,185 meters. The area is densely forested, with the lower parts having predominate oak and mixed forests (Figs. 1–5) and the higher parts

having fir forests (Figs. 7, 10–12). In the highest forestless parts, there are mountain steppes and pastures with numerous rocks or rock rubble (Figs. 8–9, 13). The area is very sparsely populated. Agriculture is basically limited to pastoralism, there are limited paved roads, and narrow dirt roads dominate, susceptible to destruction by rains, rocks and mudslides. Since historic times, this region has been considered inaccessible and difficult for field research. Tourism is also limited, and only in the 21st century it become more active. So far, there has been no data on the myrmecofauna of this region, although the mountainous nature indicates the possibility of endemic species.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

All specimens were collected during an expedition organized by the Myrmecological Laboratory, Department of Biodiversity and Evolutionary Taxonomy, University of Wrocław, on June 1-14, 2023. Material was collected by L. Borowiec, S. Salata and D. Zięcina, except for the material from localities no. 40-43a collected only by S. Salata and D. Zięcina. Most of the collecting sites were located in the Karditsa regional unit, and only a few were in the border region between the Karditsa and Evrytania units. Two additional trips were made to the city-center of Karditsa, the administrative capital of the Karditsa unit, and to the famous tourist region of Meteora, the Trikala unit, to complete data on the ants of western Thessaly.

The main method, applied at all sites, was direct sampling (hand collecting). Ant nests and individual specimens were collected on the ground, in leaf litter, under stones, in dead wood, on tree trunks and twigs. Ants were brushed off to the entomological umbrella on the roadsides and forest. Nests were also searched in rock cracks and on cracked stones using a chisel. All specimens were preserved in pure 75% and 96% ethanol.

Distribution in Greece refers to BOROWIEC (2014), SALATA and BOROWIEC (2018), and unpublished data from the Database and Collection of Greek Ants (DCGA), preserved at the University of Wrocław. When assigning distribution records to the Greek regions, we decided not to follow the country's new administrative division implemented on January 1, 2011. It is due to the fact that in the very first catalog of Greek ants (LEGAKIS 2011), distribution data was based on the old regional division, and some of records had been assigned only at the province level, without exact locality. Thus, currently it is very difficult to assign them to a specific new regional unit. Geographical coordinates are given in the decimal system. Materials are deposited in the Museum of Natural History, University of Wrocław (in temporary deposit by the Department of Biodiversity and Evolutionary Taxonomy, Myrmecological Lab). All photographs taken by S. Salata.

LIST OF LOCALITIES

The site number refers to the Locality Code used in the Database of Greek Ants stored at the Department of Biodiversity and Evolutionary Taxonomy.

Agrafa mountai region:

THE23_40 – Kalarma peak, 1958 m, 39.32263 / 21.63053, 11 VI 2023; rocky mountain peak.

THE23_41 – slope of the Voutsikaki mountain, 1344 m, 39.28217 / 21.63511, 13 VI 2023; mountain pasture.

THE23_42 – Mt Voutsikaki peak, 2134 m, 39.28040 / 21.63039, 13 VI 2023; mountain pasture.

THE23_43 – Mt Voutsikaki, 2000 m, 39.28639 / 21.62820, 13 VI 2023; mountain pasture in small valley.

THE23_43a – Voutsikaki range, 1749 m, 39.28502 / 21.65023, 13 VI 2023; mountain pasture with medium-sized rocks.

THE23_204 – Lake Plastira ad Miaritis Rooms, 804 m, 39.34343 / 21.69808, 1 VI 2023; border of oak forest and meadow.

THE23_204a – Lake Plastira ad Miaritis Rooms, 834 m, 39.34899 / 21.70207, 1 VI 2023; dirty road in oak forest.

THE23_205 – Koutsodimos, 859 m, 39.32301 / 21.6985, 2 VI 202; border of young fir forest and deciduous forest and stream valley.

THE23_206 – Filakti, 1125 m, 39.3037 / 21.67199, 2 VI 2023; bushes at border of fir forest, in umbrella.

THE23_207 – 1.1 km W of Filakti, 1164 m, 39.30425 / 21.66419, 2 VI 2023; glade in fir forest.

THE23_208 – Krioneri, 972 m, 39.32535 / 21.67907, 2 VI 2023; border of fir forest.

THE23_209 – N of Koutsodimos, 805 m, 39.32828 / 21.70035, 2 VI 2023; broad leaf oak forest.

THE_209a – Nevropoli vic., 849 m, 39.35928 / 21.69614, 2 VI 2023, oak forest.

THE23_210 – Trachilou, Ag. Nikolaos chapel, 1508 m, 39.322161 / 21.60387, 3 VI 2023; alpine pasture.

THE23_211 – Trachilou, 1 km E of Ag. Nikolaos chapel, 1558 m, 39.31919 / 21.61586, 3 VI 2023; alpine pasture with shrubs and rocks.

THE23_212 – Pallomadri loc. 1, 1719 m, 39.30772 / 21.62232, 3 VI 2023; alpine pasture with rocks.

THE23_213 – Pallomadri loc. 2, 1745 m, 39.30384 / 21.62318, 3 VI 2023; alpine pasture with rocks.

THE23_214 – Aspra Litharia, 1356 m, 39.31289 / 21.61459, 3 VI 2023; disturbed meadow with stones.

THE23_215 – Neochori, 981 m, 39.27323 / 21.73299, 3 VI 2023; stone walls and grass around chapel.

THE23_216 – 1.4 km N of Oxia, 1073 m, 39.37049 / 21.59365, 4 VI 2023; hill at roadsides with rocks and fir trees.

THE23_217 – ad Goura, 1278 m, 39.35435 / 21.57918, 4 VI 2023; scree with sparse fir trees.

THE23_218 – Tibano, 1555 m, 39.35358 / 21.57115, 4 VI 2023; alpine pasture with rocks.

THE23_219 – Fourka, 1713 m, 39.33804 / 21.56649, 4 VI 2023; alpine pasture with rocks.

THE23_220 – Ovria, 1740 m, 39.33155 / 21.56426, 4 VI 2023; roadsides in alpine area.

THE23_221 – Pezoulia, 1.2 km W of Ag. Nikolaos chapel, 1624 m, 39.32063 / 21.58958, 4 VI 2023; meadow close to beech forest.

THE23_222 – Kriopigi, 473 m, 39.37556 / 21.66743, 4 VI 2023; water source with stone walls.

THE23_223 – 970 m N of Elatos, 990 m, 39.24775 / 21.68767, 5 VI 2023; stream valley with plane trees.

THE23_224 – NW of Karvasaras, 1227 m, 39.25983 / 21.65125, 5 VI 2023; roadsides in fir forest.

THE23_225 – rd to Mega Revma, 1117 m, 39.25492 / 21.66641, 5 VI 2023; stream valley with large stones.

THE23_226 – 1.3 km N of Mega Revma, 1309 m, 39.27408 / 21.65609, 5 VI 2023; fir forest with limestone rocks.

THE23_227 – 1.1 km SE of Karvasaras, 986 m, 39.24756 / 21.67395, 5 VI 2023; fir forest.

THE23_228 – Elatos, 1195 m, 39.24037 / 21.68717, 5 VI 2023; roadsides in mountain pasture.

THE23_228a – Apolina, 1569 m, 39.21742 / 21.67154, 5 VI 2023; mountain pasture with rocks.

THE23_229 – Vragiana, 1101 m, 39.21302 / 21.63568, 6 VI 2023; fir forest with meadow.

THE23_230 – 860 m N of Vragiana, 1068 m, 39.21807 / 21.63412, 6 VI 2023; roadsides in fir forest.

THE23_231 – Koustesa, 993 m, 39.22822 / 21.62749, 6 VI 2023; from bushes arounds chapel, mostly in umbrella.

THE23_232 – N of Koustesa, 1113 m, 39.23319 / 21.62575, 6 VI 2023; roadsides in fir forest.

THE23_233 – Alogostalo loc. 1, 1344 m, 39.24281 / 21.61954, 6 VI 2023; mountain pasture with stones.

THE23_234 – Alogostalo loc. 2, 1511 m, 39.25192 / 21.62301, 6 VI 2023; mountain pasture with fir trees.

THE23_235 – Koutsopapoulo, 807 m, 39.20934 / 21.77173, 7 VI 2023; stream valley with plane trees and oak forest.

THE23_236 – 700 m SW of Anthiro, 827 m, 39.19559 / 21.74626, 7 VI 2023; stream valley with plane trees.

THE23_237 – 1.3 km S of Anthiro, 883 m, 39.18782 / 21.75206, 7 VI 2023; sunny hill with small oaks.

THE23_238 – S of Petralona, 1181 m, 39.17226 / 21.72764, 7 VI 2023; roadsides with stones in subalpine area.

THE23_239 – Petralona Massif, 1471 m, 39.16708 / 21.71621, 7 VI 2023; alpine pastures with limestone rocks.

THE23_240 – Karnopi, 1587 m, 39.1554 / 21.71323, 7 VI 2023; alpine pastures with limestone rocks.

THE23_241 – Agrafa Ski Resort, 1514 m, 39.2791 / 21.68136, 8 VI 2023; ski area with rocks and stones.

THE23_242 – 1.3 km S of Agrafa Ski Resort, 1584 m, 39.26699 / 21.6786, 8 VI 2023; mountain pastures with rocks.

THE23_243 – Pelekiti Monastery, 1312 m, 39.26157 / 21.69043, 8 VI 2023; old monastery area with stone walls and rocks.

THE23_244 – 1.5 km N of Neochori, 796 m, 39.29295 / 21.73395, 8 VI 2023; oak forest.

THE23_245 – Plaka loc. 1, 1700 m, 39.2127 / 21.68455, 9 VI 2023; alpine pastures with rocks.

THE23_246 – Plaka loc. 2, 1805 m, 39.20993 / 21.69041, 9 VI 2023; alpine pastures with rocks.

THE23_247 – Plaka loc. 3, 1808 m, 39.20498 / 21.68724, 9 VI 2023; alpine pastures with rocks.

THE23_248 – 2 km SW of Elatos, 1456 m, 39.22473 / 21.6743, 9 VI 2023; mountain pastures with rocks.

THE23_249 – near Longa, 833 m, 39.2537 / 21.71575, 9 VI 2023; rest area ad stream with stone walls.

THE23_251b – Lake Plastira N of Miaritis Rooms loc. 1, 823 m, 39.35498 / 21.70109, 14 VI 2023; oak forest.

THE23_251c – Lake Plastira N of Miaritis Rooms loc. 2, 852 m, 39.36097 / 21.70018, 14 VI 2023; meadow in oak forest.

Trikala unit:

THE23_250 – Meteora, ad Moni Rousanou, 442 m, 39.72201 / 21.63202, 10 VI 2023; hill with mediterranean oak forest.

THE23_251 – Meteora, ad St Nicolaos Anapausas, 335 m, 39.72275 / 21.62498, 10 VI 2023; hill with mediterranean oak forest.

Karditsa city:

THE23_251a – Karditsa city, 106 m, 39.36494 / 21.92819, 12 VI 2023; urban park.

LIST OF SPECIES

(species new to Thessaly marked with an asterisk)

1. *Aphaenogaster epirotes* (EMERY, 1895)

Localities: 215, 250, 251.

Note: *Aphaenogaster epirotes* is a common species, recorded from the East Aegean Islands, Epirus, the Ionian Islands, Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly, and Thrace. Population from Agrafa belongs to the northern form, characterized by predominantly reticulate sculpture of the head.

2. *Aphaenogaster ovaticeps* (EMERY, 1898)*

Localities: 250, 251.

Note: It is a western species, known only from Epirus, the Ionian Islands, Macedonia, and the Peloponnese. New to Thessaly.

3. *Aphaenogaster subterranea* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 204a, 205, 206, 207, 216, 223, 227, 229, 235, 236, 249, 250, 251.

Note: It is one of the commonest species so far noted from all Greek provinces except Crete.

4. *Aphaenogaster tristis* BOROWIEC, MENCHETTI, SALATA, VILA & ZIĘCINA, 2024

Localities: 209, 217, 224, 228, 228a.

Note: It is a recently described endemic Greek species belonging to the separate complex within the *A. subterranea* species group. Samples of specimens from this complex were noted from Cyclades (Naxos), the Ionian Islands, the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas, and Thessaly.

5. *Bothriomyrmex communista* SANTSCHI, 1919

Localities: 210, 211, 214, 215b, 224, 228, 234, 238, 239, 242, 251b.

Note: It is a common species, noted from most of the Greek provinces except Crete and Cyclades.

6. *Camponotus aethiops* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 204, 214, 215, 216, 218, 219, 225, 228, 228a, 229, 230, 231, 232, 233, 239, 241, 242, 244, 251b.

Note: It is a very common species, noted from all Greek provinces, and both natural and agricultural habitats.

7. *Camponotus atricolor* (NYLANDER, 1849)*

Locality: 209.

Note: It is a common species in northern Greece, recorded from the East Aegean Islands, Epirus, Macedonia, and Thrace. New to Thessaly. Records by LEGAKIS (2011) from the Dodecanese and the Peloponnese are doubtful and probably based on misidentifications, recent expeditions to these provinces did not confirm the occurrence of this species. Our record is first for Thessaly, and the southernmost locality in Greece.

8. *Camponotus dalmaticus* (NYLANDER, 1849)

Localities: 235, 250, 251, 251b.

Note: It is a northern and western species in Greece, known from all mainland provinces, the Ionian islands, and the East Aegean Islands. Populations from Agrafa are characterized by dark mesosoma, most specimens have only pronotum partly reddish, but often the whole mesosoma is completely black.

9. *Camponotus fallax* (NYLANDER, 1856)

Localities: 209, 217, 251c.

Note: It is an uncommon species in Greece, recorded from all mainland provinces but in island Greece known only from the East Aegean Islands and the Ionian Islands.

10. *Camponotus ionius* EMERY, 1920

Localities: 250.

Note: It is a common species in Greece, recorded from all provinces except Crete.

11. *Camponotus lateralis* (OLIVIER, 1792)

Localities: 222, 250, 251, 251c.

Note: It is one of the commonest Greek ants known from all provinces.

12. *Camponotus ligniperda* (LATREILLE, 1802)

Localities: 43a, 205, 207, 208, 209, 211, 215, 216, 223, 224, 229, 230, 234, 238, 241, 243, 249.

Note: In Greece, this species is known only from mountains of all mainland provinces except Thrace, and was also noted from the Ionian Islands.

13. *Camponotus nitidescens* FOREL, 1889*

Localities: 238, 239.

Note: It is a rare Greek endemic species noted only from the Ionian Islands, the Peloponnese, and the western units of Sterea Ellas. Reported from coniferous forests, stream valleys with mixed forest and mountain pastures with oak shrubs. New to Thessaly.

14. *Camponotus oertzeni* FOREL, 1889

Localities: 205, 207, 208, 214, 215, 225, 228, 232, 234, 235, 237, 243.

Note: It is a common species, known from all Greek provinces, often misidentified with *Camponotus aethiops*, but unlike this species, it prefers more natural habitats and avoids agricultural areas.

15. *Camponotus piceus* (LEACH, 1825)

Localities: 206, 207, 209, 210, 211, 214, 215, 222, 224, 225, 229, 231, 232, 233, 234, 238, 239, 243, 248, 250, 251.

Note: It is a common species, known from all Greek provinces.

16. *Camponotus vagus* (SCOPOLI, 1763)

Localities: 204, 205, 207, 209, 216, 225, 235, 236, 237, 238, 243, 244, 251b, 251c.

Note: It is a common species in the Greek mainland, but in islands it is known only from the East Aegean and Ionian Islands.

17. *Cataglyphis nodus* (BRULLÉ, 1833)

Localities: 204, 205, 207, 209, 232, 237, 238, 250, 251b.

Note: It is a common species known from all Greek provinces except Cyclades. The single record from Crete has been questioned (SALATA *et al.* 2020).

18. *Chalepoxenus muellerianus* (FINZI, 1922)

Localities: 40, 217, 228a, 239, 240.

Note: It is an inquiline parasite in nests of various *Temnothorax* species. Recorded from Crete, Epirus, the Ionian Islands, Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas, and Thessaly. In Agrafa, collected in a nest of an unidentified species of the *T. tuberculum* complex named in this paper as *Temnothorax* cf. *tuberculum*_long spines.

19. *Colobopsis truncata* (SPINOLA, 1808)

Localities: 209, 237, 251b, 251c.

Note: It is a common species, recorded from all Greek provinces.

20. *Crematogaster schmidtii* (MAYR, 1853)

Localities: 205, 209, 215, 222, 235, 236, 237, 244, 249, 250, 251, 251b, 251c.

Note: It is a common species, known from all Greek Provinces, common in mainland Greece and northern archipelagos but rare in southern islands.

21. *Crematogaster sordidula* (NYLANDER, 1849)

Localities: 250.

Note: It is a common species recorded from all Greek regions.

22. *Dolichoderus quadripunctatus* (LINNAEUS, 1771)

Localities: 204, 205, 209, 215, 222, 235, 236, 249, 251b.

Note: It is a moderately common species, known from all Greek provinces except Cyclades.

23. *Formica cunicularia* LATREILLE, 1798

Localities: 205, 207, 208, 211, 212, 215, 244, 251b, 251c.

Note: It is common in northern mainland provinces and moderately common in southern mainland, on islands noted only from the East Aegean Islands and Crete.

24. *Formica fusca* LINNAEUS, 1758

Localities: 40, 42, 206, 209, 219, 224, 229, 230, 231, 234, 237, 238, 239, 243, 248.

Note: *Formica fusca* is a mountain species noted from all mainland provinces, on islands known only from Crete (our unpublished data), the Ionian Islands and Euboea of Sterea Ellas. Prefers shadow mountain coniferous forests.

25. *Formica gagates* LATREILLE, 1798
 Localities: 42, 204, 205, 206, 209, 215, 216, 222, 225, 229, 231, 235, 244, 249, 251b.
 Note: It is a moderately common species known from all mainland provinces, the East Aegean and the Ionian Islands.
26. *Formica pratensis* RETZIUS, 1783
 Locality: 219.
 Note: In Greece, it is a rare species known only from alpine pastures of Macedonia, Thessaly, and Thrace.
27. *Formica rufibrabis* FABRICIUS, 1793
 Localities: 42, 205, 210, 214, 233, 234, 240, 241, 242, 243, 245, 246, 247, 248, 251c.
 Note: It is a moderately common species, recorded from all mainland provinces and the Ionian Islands.
28. *Formica sanguinea* LATREILLE, 1798
 Localities: 40a, 42, 43a, 210, 211, 212, 213, 221, 228, 234, 242, 246, 251b.
 Note: In Greece, it is a mountain species noted only from mainland provinces except Epirus.
29. *Lasius alienus* (FÖRSTER, 1850)
 Localities: 205, 207, 208, 209, 210, 211, 223, 236, 238, 239, 241, 248.
 Note: It is a common species, known from all Greek provinces but common only in northern and central mainland.
30. *Lasius balcanicus* SEIFERT, 1988 or *Lasius distinguendus* (EMERY, 1916)*
 Localities: 204, 211, 221.
 Note: Proper identification of both taxa is possible based only on the gyne caste. In Agrafa, samples with only workers were collected. Neither *L. balcanicus* nor *L. distinguendus* have been reported from Thessaly.
31. *Lasius bombycina* SEIFERT & GALKOWSKI, 2016
 Localities: 205, 206, 209, 214, 233.
 Note: It is a recently described species but known from all mainland Greek provinces and the Ionian Islands.
32. *Lasius brunneus* (LATREILLE, 1798)
 Locality: 235.
 Note: In Greece, it is a rare mountain species although it is known from all mainland provinces, also from the East Aegean and Ionian Islands.
33. *Lasius emarginatus* (OLIVIER, 1792)
 Localities: 204, 206, 207, 208, 215, 216, 217, 223, 224, 225, 227, 228, 230, 231, 232, 233, 234, 236, 237, 238, 239, 241, 243, 245, 247, 248, 251, 251b.
 Note: It is a common species in mainland Greece, known from all provinces but not recorded from island provinces where it is replaced by the sibling species *Lasius illyricus* ZIMMERMANN.
34. *Lasius flavus* (FABRICIUS, 1782)
 Localities: 43a, 205, 207, 208, 218, 222, 223, 227, 229, 236, 238, 240, 245.
 Note: In Greece, it is a moderately common, mountain species, although it is known from all mainland provinces and from the East Aegean and Ionian Islands.

35. *Lasius fuliginosus* (LATREILLE, 1798)*
Localities: 236, 244, 251b.
Note: It is a rare species, hitherto recorded only from Macedonia and Thrace. New to Thessaly.
36. *Lasius jensi* SEIFERT, 1982
Locality: 242.
Note: In Greece, it is a rare species known only from Macedonia, Thessaly, and Thrace.
37. *Lasius karpinisi* SEIFERT, 1992*
Locality: 231.
Note: A very rare species, hitherto known only from the type locality in Sterea Ellas province. New to Thessaly.
38. *Lasius lasioides* (EMERY, 1869)
Localities: 208, 223, 251c.
Note: It is a common species, known from all Greek provinces.
39. *Lasius myops* FOREL, 1894
Localities: 212, 216, 219, 232, 241, 246, 247.
Note: In Greece, it is a rare species known only from Macedonia, Thessaly, and Thrace.
40. *Lasius neglectus* VON LOON, BOOMSMA & ANDRASALVY, 1990*
Locality: 251, 251a.
Note: It is an uncommon species recorded only from the Aegean Islands, Cyclades, the Dodecanese, the Peloponnese and Thrace, mostly from urban areas and tourist resorts. New to Thessaly.
41. *Lasius nitidigaster* SEIFERT, 1996
Locality: 251c.
Note: It is a rare species recorded only from Macedonia, Thessaly, and Thrace.
42. *Lasius psammophilus* SEIFERT, 1992
Localities: 40, 40a, 41, 42, 43, 43a, 210, 212, 213, 218, 219, 221, 228a, 240, 245, 246, 248.
Note: It is a mountain species, dominant in alpine pastures on high altitudes but, at the moment, known only from Thessaly, recorded by BOROWIEC & SALATA (2018e) under the name *Lasius* cf. *neglectus*.
43. *Lasius reginae* FABER, 1967*
Locality: 208, 228, 228a, 234, 243.
Note: It is a very rare species, recorded only from the Peloponnese. New to Thessaly.
44. *Lasius sabularum* (BONDROIT, 1918)*
Localities: 205, 209.
Note: It is a rare species only recently recorded from Greek Thrace (BOROWIEC *et al.* 2023). New to Thessaly.
45. *Lepisiota frauenfeldi* (MAYR, 1855)
Localities: 250.
Note: It is a common species, recorded from all Greek provinces, but perhaps it is a complex of cryptic species.

46. *Liometopum microcephalum* (PANZER, 1798)
 Localities: 204, 209, 222, 250, 251, 251c.
 Note: It is an uncommon species, recorded from all Greek provinces except Crete, Cyclades, and the Dodecanese.
47. *Messor hellenius* AGOSTI & COLLINGWOOD, 1987
 Localities: 204, 251, 251c.
 Note: It is a species common in mainland Greece, rare on islands but known from all provinces.
48. *Messor structor* (LATREILLE, 1798)
 Localities: 207, 208, 210, 211, 212, 214, 217, 218, 219, 221, 228a, 229, 231, 234, 239, 240, 241, 242, 243, 246, 248.
 Note: It is a common species in the mountains of all mainland provinces.
49. *Messor wasmanni* KRAUSSE, 1910
 Locality: 251b.
 Note: It is a common species, known from all Greek provinces.
50. *Myrmecina graminicola* (LATREILLE, 1802)
 Localities: 205, 224, 228, 229, 233, 236, 244.
 Note: It is an uncommon species, but recorded from almost all the Greek provinces except the East Aegean Islands.
51. *Myrmica deplanata* EMERY, 1921*
 Locality: 42, 43, 43a, 44, 241.
 Note: It is an uncommon species recorded from the Ionian Islands, Macedonia, Peloponnese, and Thrace. New to Thessaly.
52. *Myrmica hellenica* FINZI, 1926
 Locality: 251a, 251c.
 Note: It is an uncommon species recorded from the Ionian Islands, Macedonia, Peloponnese, Thessaly, and Thrace.
53. *Myrmica pelops* SEIFERT, 2003*
 Localities: 242, 246.
 Note: It is a Greek endemic, known only from Peloponnese and Euboea Island of Sterea Ellas. New to Thessaly.
54. *Myrmica sabuleti* MEINERT, 1861
 Localities: 40, 206, 211, 212, 219, 221, 224, 225, 228a, 231, 233, 246, 248.
 Note: It is a moderately common species known from all mainland provinces. Record from the the Dodecanese by LEGAKIS (2011) is doubtful and has not been confirmed in recent studies on these islands.
55. *Myrmica scabrinodis* NYLANDER, 1846
 Localities: 223, 228, 229, 243, 244, 251b, 251c.
 Note: It is an uncommon species, recorded from all mainland provinces except Epirus and from the Ionian Islands. In northern Greece, it is known from lowland and mountain habitats, in southern Greece only in mountains.

56. *Pheidole* cf. *pallidula*

Localities: 204, 205, 209, 216, 222, 225, 232, 237, 243, 250, 251, 251b.

Note: Mediterranean populations of the taxon named *Pheidole pallidula* have recently been divided into four species, three of them recorded in Greece (SEIFERT 2016), but this revision is still under discussion owing to the great local variability of this very common Mediterranean ant. Specimens from Agrafa have characters of *Pheidole balcanica* SEIFERT, 2016.

57. *Plagiolepis perperamus* SALATA, BOROWIEC & RADCHENKO, 2018

Localities: 204, 207, 216, 237, 239, 251c.

Note: It is an uncommon species but recorded from all Greek provinces, often collected in anthropogenic habitats in tourist resorts and cities.

58. *Plagiolepis pygmaea* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 205, 206, 208, 209, 211, 214, 217, 219, 222, 224, 225, 228, 228a, 229, 231, 232, 233, 234, 236, 237, 238, 239, 250, 251, 251b.

Note: It is the most common and ubiquitous species of the genus *Plagiolepis*, known from all Greek provinces.

59. *Plagiolepis taurica* SANTSCHI, 1920

Localities: 210, 221, 248.

Note: According to the recent conception of species of the *Plagiolepis taurica* group by KIRSCHNER *et al.* (2020) in Europe occur three taxa from this complex, two of them: *P. taurica* SANTSCHI, 1920 and *P. pallescens* FOREL, 1889 have been reported from Greece. A re-examination of materials from mainland Greece showed that in the Greek mainland, including Thessaly, occurs only *P. taurica*.

60. *Plagiolepis xene* STÄRCKE, 1936*

Localities: 251.

Note: It is a rare inquiline parasite in nests of other *Plagiolepis* species. Recorded from the East Aegean Islands, Epirus, the Ionian Islands, and Macedonia. New to Thessaly, a single gyne was collected in a nest of *Plagiolepis pygmaea*.

61. *Polyergus rufescens* (LATREILLE, 1798)*

Localities: 230, 239.

Note: It is a very rare species, hitherto known only from Macedonia. New to Thessaly.

62. *Ponera coarctata* (LATREILLE, 1802)

Localities: 210, 216, 224, 228, 228a, 240, 245, 248.

Note: It is a common species in Greek mainland provinces but from islands known only from the Ionian Islands.

63. *Prenolepis nitens* (MAYR, 1853)

Localities: 205, 206, 225, 231, 235.

Note: It is a common species in mainland Greece, in islands noted only from the East Aegean and Ionian Islands.

64. *Proformica borowieci* LEBAS, GALKOWSKI, LENOIR & PERDEREAU, 2023*

Localities: 218, 220.

Note: It is a recently described species known only from the Mt. Parnassos of Sterea Ellas. New to Thessaly.

65. *Solenopsis juliae* ARAKELIAN, 1991

Localities: 205, 210, 211, 218, 224, 228a, 231, 233, 238, 242, 248, 251c.

Note: The status of most European species of the genus *Solenopsis* requires extensive revision. GALKOWSKI *et al.* (2010) redescribed *Solenopsis fugax* and suggested that four distinct species groups occur in Europe and the Mediterranean region. Recently, Csósz *et al.* (2023), clarified the status of East European and Balkan species of the *S. fugax* complex and populations recorded from Greece under the name *Solenopsis cf. lusitanica* should be named *Solenopsis juliae* ARAKELIAN, 1991. They were recorded from all Greek provinces except Crete.

66. *Stenamma debile* (FÖRSTER, 1850)

Locality: 223, 227.

Note: It is a rare species recorded from the East Aegean Islands, Crete, Cyclades, the Ionian Islands, Macedonia, Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas, and Thessaly.

67. *Tapinoma glabrella* NYLANDER, 1849

Localities: 204, 205, 206, 207, 208, 209, 211, 212, 214, 215, 216, 218, 219, 221, 228a, 233, 234, 237, 238, 239, 241, 242, 246, 247, 248, 251b, 251c.

Note: According to the recent revision of the Palaearctic members of the genus *Tapinoma* (SEIFERT *et al.* 2024) populations of the *Tapinoma erraticum* complex from the Balkan Peninsula recorded under name *Tapinoma cf. erraticum*_BALC should be named *Tapinoma glabrella* NYLANDER. In Greece, this is a common species, known from all Greek provinces.

68. *Temnothorax albipennis* (CURTIS, 1854)*

Localities: 211, 216, 217, 228a, 230, 231, 239, 245, 251b.

Note: Due to taxonomic uncertainties regarding the *Temnothorax unifasciatus* complex in the Balkans, it was not recorded from Greece. Only recently it was recorded for the first time from the Peloponnese (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2023). New to Thessaly.

69. *Temnothorax arkasi* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2022*

Localities: 240.

Note: It is a recently described species hitherto known only from Peloponnese. New to Thessaly.

70. *Temnothorax cf. aveli**

Localities: 222, 237, 251b.

Note: It is an undescribed species of the *T. aveli* group known from recent material collected in Agrafa and in Thrace.

71. *Temnothorax bulgaricus* (FOREL, 1892)

Localities: 251a.

Note: It is a common species noted from the most Greek provinces except Crete and Cyclades.

72. *Temnothorax clypeatus* (MAYR, 1853)*

Localities: 251a.

Note: It is a very rare species, recorded only from the Ionian Islands. New to Thessaly.

73. *Temnothorax crassispinus* (KARAVAEV, 1926)*

Localities: 206, 207, 209, 215, 217, 223, 226, 227, 228a, 230, 231, 233, 234, 235, 236, 238, 243, 244, 249.

Note: In Greece, occur two sibling species belonging to the *T. nylanderi* species group: *T. crassispinus* (KARAVAIEV) and *T. crasecundus* SEIFERT & CSŐSZ. They are mostly separated geographically with narrow zone of sympatric occurrence. *Temnothorax crassispinus* was recorded from Epirus, the Ionian Islands, western Macedonia, western Peloponnese, and western Sterea Ellas. New to Thessaly, where it occurs only in the mountains of the western part of this province, in the eastern massifs of Thessaly only *T. crasecundus* occurs (see BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018).

74. *Temnothorax graecus* (FOREL, 1911)*

Localities: 250, 251a, 251b, 251c.

Note: It is a moderately common species known from mainland provinces except Epirus, Cyclades, the Dodecanese, and the Ionian Islands. New to Thessaly.

75. *Temnothorax helenae* CSŐSZ, HEINZE & MIKÓ, 2015

Localities: 236, 250, 251a, 251b, 251c.

Note: It is a moderately common species known from mainland provinces except Epirus and from Cyclades.

76. *Temnothorax lichtensteini* (BONDROIT, 1918)

Localities: 207, 209, 216, 228, 248, 250, 251.

Note: It is a moderately common species known from all mainland provinces (except Peloponnese), and from the Ionian Islands.

77. *Temnothorax* cf. *melanocephalus*

Localities: 40, 42, 43, 211, 219, 234, 240, 242, 145, 246.

Note: It is a member of the *Temnothorax tuberum* complex. The complex appears to be speciose in Greece, and the status of most taxa is unclear and needs comprehensive revision. Morphospecies named *T. cf. melanocephalus* is restricted to the alpine areas of several mountain ranges of Macedonia, Peloponnese, and Thessaly.

78. *Temnothorax messiniaensis* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2019*

Localities: 207, 209, 232, 237, 251b.

Note: It is a recently described species, endemic to Greece, and common in the Ionian Islands and Peloponnese. New to Thessaly.

79. *Temnothorax morea* CSŐSZ, SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2018*

Localities: 250, 251, 251c.

Note: It is a recently described species, hitherto noted only from Epirus, the Ionian Islands, and the Peloponnese. New to Thessaly.

80. *Temnothorax* cf. *nigriceps* _darkened femora

Localities: 40, 40a, 41, 42, 43a, 212, 213, 218, 219, 221, 228a, 234, 240, 241, 242, 245, 246, 247.

Note: Our study of various Greek samples of the *Temnothorax nigriceps* complex showed that there are at least three morphospecies, and probably none of them is conspecific with true *T. nigriceps* (MAYR, 1855). This problem will be clarified in a forthcoming revision of this group of species. All morphospecies of this group were noted from alpine parts of all Greek mainland mountains and the highest parts of the Ionian Islands.

81. *Temnothorax parnonensis* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2022*

Locality: 41.

Note: It is species recently described based on samples collected from Mainalo, Parnon, and Taygetos mountain ridges of Peloponnese in 2000 (SALATA & BOROWIEC 2022), and confirmed from Mainalo and Parnon Mts in materials collected in 2023 (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2023). New to Thessaly.

82. *Temnothorax recedens* (NYLANDER, 1856)

Locality: 222, 250, 251.

Note: It is a common species known from all Greek provinces.

83. *Temnothorax rogeri* EMERY, 1869*

Localities: 237.

Note: It is a western species, recorded from Epirus, the Ionian Islands, western Peloponnese, and western Sterea Ellas. New to Thessaly.

84. *Temnothorax semiruber* (ANDRÉ, 1881)

Localities: 205, 210, 211, 216, 217, 224, 225, 228a, 231, 232, 234, 237, 239, 241, 243.

Note: It is an uncommon species, although recorded from all Greek provinces except the Ionian Islands.

85. *Temnothorax* cf. *tauricus*

Localities: 236, 237, 243, 251b.

Note: Although Csösz *et al.* (2024) synonymized *Temnothorax tauricus* (RUZSKY, 1902) with *T. unifasciatus* (LATREILLE, 1798), Greek populations hitherto identified as *T. tauricus* appear to be a distinct species from *T. unifasciatus* and its status needs revision based on molecular data. It is a mountain morphospecies known from mainland provinces and the Ionian Islands.

86. *Temnothorax tergestinus* (FINZI, 1928)

Localities: 217, 228a, 243.

Note: It is a mountain species known from mainland provinces except Sterea Ellas.

87. *Temnothorax* cf. *tergestinus* sp. 1*

Locality: 228a.

Note: It is an undescribed species of the *T. nylanderi* species group known only from the Agrafa mountain region.

88. *Temnothorax* cf. *tergestinus* sp. 2*

Localities: 247.

Note: It is the second undescribed species of the *T. nylanderi* species group known only from the Agrafa mountain region.

89. *Temnothorax* cf. *tubenum*_long spines

Localities: 205, 206, 210, 211, 214, 215, 216, 217, 218, 219, 224, 225, 228, 228a, 231, 233, 234, 236, 237, 238, 239, 240, 241, 242, 243, 246, 248, 251b

Note: In Greece, occur at least three morphospecies of the *Temnothorax tubenum* complex. All probably represent undescribed taxa, but this hypothesis should be verified by comprehensive revision. The morphospecies named *Temnothorax* cf. *tubenum*_long spines appears to be common in the mountains of Peloponnese and Thessaly.

90. *Temnothorax turcicus* (SANTSCHI, 1934)

Localities: 205, 206, 215, 228a, 231, 244.

Note: It is an uncommon arboricole species, recorded from the Aegean Islands, Macedonia, Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly, and Thrace.

91. *Temnothorax unifasciatus* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 206, 207, 208, 209, 209a, 222, 228, 234, 235, 241, 244, 246, 251b.

Note: Status of Greek populations of the *Temnothorax unifasciatus* complex is unclear and needs comprehensive revision. They differ from typical *Temnothorax unifasciatus* from Central Europe in the antennal club only slightly infuscate or completely yellow and in dark posterior band on first gastral tergite often narrowed in the middle or almost interrupted. At first glance, many specimens look similar to typically colored specimens of *T. turcicus* but differ in petrofile habitat preference and nesting in rock crevices.

92. *Tetramorium caespitum* (LINNAEUS, 1758)

Localities: 40, 41, 42, 43, 43a, 208, 209, 211, 214, 228a, 240, 245, 248.

Note: A recent revision of the *Tetramorium caespitum* complex (WAGNER *et al.* 2017) showed that the group contains several cryptic species, thus all old Greek records of *Tetramorium caespitum* need confirmation. SALATA & BOROWIEC (2019c) confirmed its occurrence in Epirus, Macedonia, Peloponnese, Thessaly, and later also noted from Sterea Ellas.

93. *Tetramorium chefketi* FOREL, 1911

Locality: 240.

Note: It is an uncommon species recorded from the Aegean Islands, Crete, the Ionian Islands, Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Thessaly, and Thrace.

94. *Tetramorium ferox* RUZSKY, 1903*

Localities: 214, 224.

Note: It is a rare species, known from the Aegean Islands, Crete, Dodecanese, the Ionian Islands, Macedonia, and Thrace. New to Thessaly.

95. *Tetramorium* cf. *flavidulum*

Locality: 213, 233, 239, 241.

Note: It is a mountain species of unclear status, recorded from alpine parts of mountains of Macedonia, Sterea Ellas, and Thessaly. It distinctly differs from *Tetramorium flavidulum* EMERY, 1924 known from the East Aegean Islands in smaller size and yellowish brown to dark brown body. Probably it is a Greek mountain endemic.

96. *Tetramorium impurum* (FÖRSTER, 1850)

Locality: 213, 228a.

Note: Mountain species, recorded from alpine parts of mountains of all mainland provinces and from the Ionian Islands.

97. *Tetramorium indocile* SANTSCHI, 1927*

Localities: 204, 207, 210, 212, 218, 219, 221, 234, 242, 246.

Note: Its status was clarified recently, but probably it is a common species in mediterranean habitats. Recorded from Crete, the Dodecanese, Macedonia, the Peloponnese, and Thrace. New to Thessaly.

98. *Tetramorium kephalosi* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2017

Locality: 233, 237.

Note: It is a recently described and common species, known from all Greek provinces.

99. *Tetramorium moravicum* KRATOCHVIL, 1941

Localities: 204, 205, 207, 208, 209, 211, 214, 215, 218, 221, 223, 224, 225, 228, 229, 230, 231, 234, 235, 236, 238, 239, 241, 243, 244, 247, 251, 251c.

Note: It is a common species known from all mainland provinces but absent in islands.

DISCUSSION

In the first paper on ants from Thessaly province 107 species and morphospecies were recorded (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018e). The material used in this work came mainly from the two eastern regional units: Larissa and Magnezia (40 collecting sites), and only one site came from the western unit of Trikala. The material from the 2023 collecting trips came exclusively from the western parts of Thessaly, the Karditsa unit, and two sites from the Trikala unit. As a result of these new explorations, the number of known species and morphospecies of Thessalian ants increased to 134:

UPDATED CHECKLIST OF ANTS RECORDED FROM THESSALY

(species new to Thessaly marked with an asterisk)

1. *Acropyga paleartica* MENOZZI
2. *Aphaenogaster epirotes* (EMERY)
3. *Aphaenogaster ovaticeps* (EMERY)*
4. *Aphaenogaster subterranea* (LATREILLE)
5. *Aphaenogaster tristis* BOROWIEC, MENCHETTI, SALATA, VILA & ZIĘCINA
6. *Bothriomyrmex communista* SANTSCHI
7. *Camponotus aethiops* (LATREILLE)
8. *Camponotus atricolor* (NYLANDER)*
9. *Camponotus dalmaticus* (NYLANDER)
10. *Camponotus fallax* (NYLANDER)
11. *Camponotus gestroi* EMERY
12. *Camponotus ionius* EMERY
13. *Camponotus lateralis* (OLIVIER)
14. *Camponotus ligniperda* (LATREILLE)
15. *Camponotus nitidescens* FOREL*
16. *Camponotus oertzeni* FOREL
17. *Camponotus piceus* (LEACH)
18. *Camponotus vagus* (SCOPOLI)
19. *Cataglyphis hellenica* (FOREL)
20. *Cataglyphis nodus* (BRULLÉ)
21. *Chalepoxenus muellerianus* (FINZI)
22. *Colobopsis truncata* (SPINOLA)
23. *Crematogaster ionia* FOREL
24. *Crematogaster lorteti* FOREL
25. *Crematogaster schmidtii* (MAYR)

26. *Crematogaster sordidula* (NYLANDER)
27. *Dolichoderus quadripunctatus* (LINNAEUS)
28. *Formica clara* FOREL
29. *Formica cunicularia* LATREILLE
30. *Formica fusca* LINNAEUS
31. *Formica gagates* LATREILLE
32. *Formica pratensis* RETZIUS
33. *Formica rufibarbis* FABRICIUS
34. *Formica sanguinea* LATREILLE
35. *Lasius alienus* (FÖRSTER)
36. *Lasius* cf. *balcanicus* or *distinguendus**
37. *Lasius bombycina* SEIFERT & GALKOWSKI
38. *Lasius brunneus* (LATREILLE)
39. *Lasius citrinus* EMERY
40. *Lasius emarginatus* (OLIVIER)
41. *Lasius flavus* (FABRICIUS)
42. *Lasius fuliginosus* (LATREILLE)*
43. *Lasius jensi* SEIFERT
44. *Lasius karpinisi* SEIFERT*
45. *Lasius lasioides* (EMERY)
46. *Lasius myops* FOREL
47. *Lasius neglectus* VON LOON, BOOMSMA & ANDRASFALVY*
48. *Lasius nitidigaster* SEIFERT
49. *Lasius psammophilus* SEIFERT
50. *Lasius reginae* FABER*
51. *Lasius sabularum* (BONDROIT)*
52. *Lasius turcicus* SANTSCHI*
53. *Lepisiota frauenfeldi* (MAYR)
54. *Liometopum microcephalum* (PANZER)
55. *Manica rubida* (LATREILLE)
56. *Messor hellenius* AGOSTI & COLLINGWOOD
57. *Messor ibericus* SANTSCHI
58. *Messor mcarthuri* SCHLICK *et al.*
59. *Messor structor* (LATREILLE)
60. *Messor wasmanni* KRAUSSE
61. *Metasius myrmidon* (MEI)
62. *Myrmecina graminicola* (LATREILLE)
63. *Myrmica deplanata* EMERY*
64. *Myrmica hellenica* FINZI

65. *Myrmica lobicornis* NYLANDER
66. *Myrmica pelops* SEIFERT*
67. *Myrmica sabuleti* MEINERT
68. *Myrmica scabrinodis* NYLANDER
69. *Myrmica sulcinodis* NYLANDER
70. *Myrmoxenus gordiagini* RUZSKY
71. *Myrmoxenus ravouxi* (ANDRÉ)
72. *Pheidole* cf. *pallidula*
73. *Plagiolepis perperamus* SALATA, BOROWIEC & RADCHENKO
74. *Plagiolepis pygmaea* (LATREILLE)
75. *Plagiolepis taurica* SANTSCHI
76. *Plagiolepis xene* STÄRCKE*
77. *Polyergus rufescens* (LATREILLE)*
78. *Ponera coarctata* (LATREILLE)
79. *Ponera testacea* EMERY
80. *Prenolepis nitens* (MAYR)
81. *Proformica borowieci* LEBAS, GALKOWSKI, LENOIR & PERDEREAU*
82. *Proformica lebasi* BOROWIEC & SALATA
83. *Solenopsis* cf. *lusitanica*
84. *Stenamma debile* (FÖRSTER)
85. *Stenamma striatulum* EMERY
86. *Tapinoma glabrella* NYLANDER
87. *Temnothorax affinis* (MAYR)
88. *Temnothorax albipennis* (CURTIS)*
89. *Temnothorax arkasi* SALATA & BOROWIEC*
90. *Temnothorax* cf. *aveli**
91. *Temnothorax brackoi* SALATA & BOROWIEC
92. *Temnothorax bulgaricus* (FOREL)
93. *Temnothorax clypeatus* (MAYR)*
94. *Temnothorax crasecundus* SEIFERT & CSÓSZ
95. *Temnothorax crassispinus* (KARAVAIEV)*
96. *Temnothorax* cf. *exilis*
97. *Temnothorax flavicornis* (EMERY)
98. *Temnothorax graecus* (FOREL)*
99. *Temnothorax helenae* CSÓSZ, HEINZE & MIKÓ
100. *Temnothorax* cf. *kemali*
101. *Temnothorax lichtensteini* (BONDROIT)
102. *Temnothorax* cf. *melanocephalus*
103. *Temnothorax messiniaensis* SALATA & BOROWIEC*

104. *Temnothorax morea* CSŐSZ, SALATA & BOROWIEC*
105. *Temnothorax* cf. *nigriceps*_darkened femora
106. *Temnothorax parnonensis* SALATA & BOROWIEC*
107. *Temnothorax parvulus* (SCHENCK)
108. *Temnothorax recedens* (NYLANDER)
109. *Temnothorax rogeri* EMERY*
110. *Temnothorax semiruber* (ANDRÉ)
111. *Temnothorax sordidulus* (MÜLLER)
112. *Temnothorax strymonensis* CSŐSZ, SALATA & BOROWIEC
113. *Temnothorax subtilis* CSŐSZ, HEINZE & MIKÓ
114. *Temnothorax tauricus* (RUZSKY)
115. *Temnothorax tergestinus* (FINZI)
116. *Temnothorax* cf. *tergestinus* sp. 1*
117. *Temnothorax* cf. *tergestinus* sp. 2*
118. *Temnothorax* cf. *tuberum*_long spines
119. *Temnothorax tuberum* (FABRICIUS)
120. *Temnothorax turcicus* (SANTSCHI)
121. *Temnothorax unifasciatus* (LATREILLE)
122. *Tetramorium caespitum* (LINNAEUS)
123. *Tetramorium chefketi* FOREL
124. *Tetramorium diomedea* EMERY
125. *Tetramorium ferox* RUZSKY*
126. *Tetramorium* cf. *flavidulum* EMERY
127. *Tetramorium hungaricum* RÖSZLER
128. *Tetramorium immigrans* SANTSCHI
129. *Tetramorium impurum* (FÖRSTER)
130. *Tetramorium indocile* SANTSCHI*
131. *Tetramorium kephalosi* SALATA & BOROWIEC
132. *Tetramorium moravicum* KRATOCHVÍL
133. *Tetramorium* cf. *punicum*
134. *Trichomyrmex perplexus* (RADCHENKO)

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Figs. 1–2. Oak forests north of Lake Plastira c. 830 m.

Figs. 3–4. Mixed forests: typical young forest in the Koutsodimos area c. 860 m (3), mixed plane and fir forest in a stream valley near Karvasaras c. 980 m (4).

Fig. 5. Dense mixed forest by a mountain stream near Anthiro c. 820 m.

Figs. 6–7. Forests at the upper timberline: boundary area between beech forest and mountain pasture 1.2 km W of Ag. Nikolaos Chapel c. 1600 m (6), fir forest at the upper forest line near Karvasaras c. 1200 m (7).

Figs. 8–9. Mountain pastures: at Kazarma pass approx. 1700 m above sea level (8), at Nyala pass c. 1800 m (9).

Figs. 10–11. Fir forests at the upper forest line: at the chapel of Ag. Nikolaos c. 1500 m (10), at Ouvia pass c. 1740 m (11).

Figs. 12–13. A mountain valley with sparse fir trees at Passo Tympanos c. 1550 m (12), rock terraces on the summit of Agrafa Mountain Refuge c. 1600 m (13).

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